

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies on pyrazole connected tetrahydroquinoline derivatives

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Abstract : 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydroquinolines based heterocycles connected pyrazole moieties have been synthesized using imino Diels-Alder reaction. Herein, the pyrazole substituted imines have been prepared *in situ* using 4-formyl-1,3-diphenyl pyrazole and substituted anilines, followed by a reaction with dihydropyran and dihydrofuran as dienophiles. The reactions are found to be simple to execute with high yields. The resulting tetrahydroquinoline derivatives show moderate to good antibacterial activity.

Keywords : Tetrahydroquinoline, pyrazole, Diels-Alder, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The pyranoquinoline moiety is present in many alkaloids such as flindersine, oricine and verprisine¹ and derivatives of these alkaloids possess a wide range of biological activities such as psychotropic², antiallergenic³ and antiinflammatory⁴ activities. The furoquinoline skeleton is present in many alkaloids like skimmianine and balfouridine^{5,6}. Among the currently available synthetic methodologies, the imino Diels-Alder reaction is the most enabling and versatile approach to functionalize 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolines⁷. The reaction can be carried out in one-pot fashion starting from an aniline, an aldehyde, and an electron-rich alkene, which is known as one of the three-component reactions. Activation of *N*-aryaldimines toward cycloadditions with alkenes is required. Lanthanide triflates, Lewis acids, and protic acids are the catalysts of choice.

Pyrazole represent a key motif in heterocyclic chemistry and occupy a prime place in medicinal and pesticide chemistry due to their capability to exhibit a wide range of bioactivities such as antimicrobial⁸, antitumor⁹, insecticides and fungicides¹⁰.

Results and discussion

Regarding the synthesis, imino Diels-Alder reaction has been utilized. The procedure invokes *in situ* forma-

tion of imine between 4-formyl-1,3-diphenyl pyrazole and substituted anilines, followed by a reaction with dihydropyran as dienophiles. The reactions are found to be rather simple to execute with high yields.

Additionally, we also performed antibacterial activity studies for each compound in comparison with the standard vancomycin. The studies were performed using the standard well diffusion assay and MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration) studies. However, the above molecules showed no activity against MRSA. The results showed all the molecules have moderate to good antibacterial activity. Herein, we report the synthesis and antibacterial studies of the 1,3-diphenyl pyrazole and tetrahydropyran substituted tetrahydroquinolines derivatives and their antibacterial activities.

In well diffusion method, an antibacterial assay is to detect the activity of pyrazole connected tetrahydroquinoline compounds against human bacterial pathogens. In the present work, the zone of inhibition is higher in 0.25 mg of derivative compounds from **5d**, **6d**, **7d**, **8d** shows activity against various human pathogens (*B. subtilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumonia* and *S. aureus*). The MIC results of pyrazole derivatives are showing activity against *B. subtilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumonia*, and *S. aureus*. The MICs were checked only for eight compounds, which have shown promising activity in the

Scheme 1. Synthesis of pyrazole connected 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline derivatives.

well diffusion assay. The MIC values for the pyrazole derivatives are shown in the Table 2, of which, the compound **8d** has the lowest inhibition concentration. For *P. aeruginosa* it shows 125 mg.

Experimental

Aldehyde **1** (1 mM) and aniline (**2a-d**, 1 mM) were taken in 10 mL of a mixture of acetonitrile and dichloromethane (8 : 2) stirred at rt for 1 h and then 1 mM of dihydropyran and 0.1 mM of borontrifluoride etherate were charged and stirred for 6 h. After the completion of the reaction, reaction mass quenched with ice and extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 mL). The or-

Table 1. Pyrazole connected 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline derivatives

Sr. no.	Aldehyde	Dienophile	Product <i>cis</i> : <i>trans</i>	Yield (%)	Time (h)
1.		3	60 : 40	90	7.0
2.		3	65 : 35	85	8.0
3.		3	60 : 40	89	8.0
4.		3	55 : 45	80	6.5
5.		4	58 : 42	92	7.0
6.		4	60 : 40	87	7.5
7.		4	55 : 45	90	7.5
8.		4	60 : 40	82	7.0

Table 2. Minimum inhibitory concentration

Compds.	Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) (mg/ml)			
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
6a	2.500	2.500	2.500	2.500
6b	1.250	1.250	2.500	2.500
6c	1.250	2.500	1.250	1.250
6d	1.000	1.000	2.500	1.250
8a	2.500	1.250	2.500	2.500
8b	1.250	2.500	2.500	2.500
8c	1.250	2.500	2.500	1.250
8d	0.250	0.125	0.250	0.500
Vancomycin (1 mg/mL)	0.100	0.050	1.250	0.250

ganic layer was dried and concentrated to give the crude product that was purified through silica gel (230–400 mesh) column chromatography to give the pure diastereomers. The stereochemistry of the products was assigned based on the scalar-coupling constant by NMR. All the compounds are characterized by NMR and mass spectrum.

Cis adduct **5a** :

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.14 (1H, s), 7.79–7.81 (2H, d), 7.65–7.67 (2H, d), 7.39–7.51 (6H, m), 7.34–7.30 (1H, m), 7.28–7.30 (1H, t), 6.81–6.84 (1H, t), 6.57–6.59 (1H, d), 5.28–5.29 (1H, d), 4.92 (1H, d), 3.87 (1H, brs), 3.62–3.65 (1H, t), 3.43–3.49 (1H, t), 2.25–2.27 (1H, m), 1.58–1.71 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 151.10, 145.20, 139.94, 133.07, 129.48,

128.72, 128.27, 128.16, 128.08, 127.79, 126.88, 126.50, 121.37, 120.34, 118.94, 118.72, 114.47, 72.42, 60.65, 51.26, 36.79, 25.43, 18.27; MS m/z 408 (M+H)⁺.

Trans adduct 6a :

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.1 (1H, s), 7.84–7.74 (4H, m), 7.54–7.39 (5H, m), 7.32–7.28 (1H, t), 7.25–7.22 (1H, d), 7.16–7.12 (1H, t), 6.74–6.73 (1H, t), 6.62–6.60 (1H, d), 5.05–5.02 (1H, d), 4.38 (1H, d), 4.24 (1H, br s), 3.92–3.89 (1H, d), 3.64–3.57 (1H, m), 2.11–2.07 (1H, m), 1.66–1.06 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 152.70, 144.36, 139.98, 133.24, 130.93, 129.69, 129.44, 129.36, 128.98, 128.77, 128.69, 128.63, 128.17, 126.75, 126.49, 123.01, 120.80, 119.78, 118.88, 117.74, 114.23, 74.43, 68.40, 45.86, 39.25, 24.35, 21.64; MS m/z 408 (M+H)⁺.

Minimum inhibition assay :

This minimum inhibitory concentration is the combined modified of Sarker *et al.* (2007) and Gabrielson *et al.* (2002). Volume of 100 μL of test material in 10% (v/v) DMSO or sterile water (usually a stock concentration of 1 mg/mL for purified compounds and 10 mg/mL for crude extracts) was pipetted into the first row of the plate. To all other wells 50 μL of nutrient broth or normal saline was added. Serial dilutions were performed using a multi channel pipette and the concentration of compound for serial dilution is 10 mg in the first row and Tips were discarded after use such that each well had 50 μL of the test material in serially descending concentrations. To each well 10 μL of 2,3-bis[2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulphophenyl]-2H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide inner salt (MTT) indicator solution was added. Using a pipette 30 μL of 3.3 × strength isosensitised broths was added to each well to ensure that the final volume was single strength of the nutrient broth. Finally, 10 μL of bacterial suspension (5 × 10⁶ cfu/mL) was added to each well to achieve a concentration of 5 × 10⁵ cfu/mL. Each plate was wrapped loosely with cling film to ensure that bacteria did not become dehydrated. Each plate had a positive control (Ciprofloxacin in serial dilution) in first column and the last two columns C₁ and C₂, comprising Muller hinton broth + Indicator, with and without the bacterial

suspension, respectively. The plates were prepared in triplicate, and placed in an incubator set at 37 °C for 18–24 h. Then the color change was assessed visually. This (XTT) tetrazolium salt assay measures the cells ability to convert the tetrazolium salt to the formazan product. Any colour changes from yellow to red were recorded as positive. The lowest concentration was taken as MIC value.

Conclusion

In summary, we have demonstrated a high yielding approach involving imino Diels-Alder reaction to synthesize pyrazole substituted tetrahydroquinolines derivatives. Antimicrobial studies of these compounds showed promising results. The operational simplicity of this method and the high yields of the product make it attractive for the synthesis of this class of potential biologically active molecules.

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